

What Drives Smartphone Purchase Intention? Perspective from Technology, Price, and E-Wom as Mediators

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Abstract:- Despite the fact that smartphones have been commonly used by everyone in recent years, the market share of some smartphones is declining. The study evaluated technology and pricing through e-wom to suggest some improvements to improve smartphone purchase intentions. The online survey was created and conveyed on social media to collect data and obtained 311 respondents of smartphone users in Jabodetabek. This research method uses quantitative methods with the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with the Smart PLS 3.0 program. The results of this study reveal that technology, price, and e-wom directly affect smartphone purchase intentions. On the other hand, the price has a significant effect on e-wom, but technology does not significantly affect e-wom. The e-wom variable can mediate between price and smartphone purchase intent, but e-wom cannot mediate between technology and smartphone purchase intention.

Keywords:- Technology, Price, E-Wom, Purchase Intention, Smartphone.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays smartphones are becoming part of a tool that creates life less demanding for individuals all over the world. Smartphones play an important role in monitoring new technologies that can affect changes in social behavior and consumer lifestyles [1]. The need to communicate and access information is increasingly making smartphones a must-have item. The choice of types and specifications offered is increasingly diverse and interesting [2]. In addition, there is a survey, there is an increase in smartphone users globally. Smartphone users in 2016 were 3.6 billion and are projected to continue to increase to 7.6 billion smartphone users in 2027 [3]. Experts have speculated that the distribution of smartphones will surpass computers due to factors of portability and flexibility functions [4].

Smartphone users in Indonesia are also growing rapidly. In 2011 smartphone users in Indonesia amounted to 11.7 million and this continued to increase until it reached 89.86 million in 2022 [3]. Indonesia is the nation with the fourth biggest smartphone users within the world after China, India, and America [5]. In its development, there are several

smartphone brands in Indonesia, namely Samsung, Xiaomi, Oppo, Apple, and others. There is a market share of several smartphone brands in Indonesia from 2017 to 2021 [6]. It can be seen that two brands continue to increase significantly, namely Apple with an average increase of 20% and Oppo by 17%, while Xiaomi in the year increased in 2017-2019 and decreased in 2020-2021. The Samsung brand experienced a decrease in market share from 2017 to 2021 with an average decline of 8%.

Low-end smartphones or commonly referred to as the lower class are market segmented and targeted at consumers who have a limited budget, with a price range of Rp. 1,000,000 – Rp. 2,000,000. High-end or high-end has a selling price range of up to more than Rp. 10,000,000. Samsung itself has several series that have a price range ranging from one million to two twenty million [7]. The Galaxy Series M and A fall into the low-end category. The Galaxy Series S, Galaxy Series Z, and Galaxy Note fall into the high-end category.

In this case, Samsung has some of the closest competitors in the two categories of low-end smartphones and high-end smartphones, where some of these competitors are included in the market share data above. The closest competitor of Samsung in the low-end category is Xiaomi [8][9][10][11][12][13]. Meanwhile, the closest competitor of Samsung in the high-end category is Apple [8][9][10][13][14][15][16]. From the results of the preliminary survey that has been carried out, three variables that have the highest value are obtained, namely technology & price which will be used as independent variables. For e-wom it is used as a mediation variable.

II. LITERATURE

A. Smartphone

Smartphones can be characterized as devices that allow users to form phone calls, recordings, and various other features. In addition, users can also perform previously unenforceable activities such as sending and receiving emails, changing archives (Word, Excel and others), browsing the internet, navigating, listening to music, reading information, health monitoring, and others [17]. The features and applications in smartphones make it less demanding for individuals to live each life they have, be it for daily activities,

work or for entertainment, and until presently the features on smartphones proceed to be developed by smartphone brands.

B. Technology

In technology, product features are characterized as product attributes utilized to meet consumer needs and desires through the usefulness and benefits of the product. Smartphone features/applications are used to make it easier for consumers to carry out their activities, both through convenience and benefits. The convenience in question includes operating smartphone technology and studying the features of smartphones. The benefits of the technology incorporate the quality of the hardware or equipment, such as battery life, storage memory, sound devices, and software, such as operating systems (android, iOS, etc.). It also includes flexibility in using various features on smartphones [18].

C. Price

Price is an important factor for studying customer intentions. Price can be characterized as the proportionate financial esteem for a product or service or the entire esteem that a customer trades for the reason of owning or utilizing that individual's product or service [18]. Price can be utilized as a thought to decide deals and the monetary capacity that customers have [19]. Warranty is one of the factors used by consumers in buying gadgets online, apart from product reviews, seller ratings, customer reviews, payment methods, and shipping methods [20].

D. E-Wom

The information process through the central channel focuses on the core of the message or the content information and description of the message content in detail and clearly informative. E-wom plays an imperative part in affecting consumers' demeanors towards brands and their intention to purchase them [21]. When the consumer has the intention to buy smartphones, the consumer will read reviews on online websites as well as social media. This can be done by the customer to ensure that the purchase intention is correct [17].

E. Purchase Intention

Purchase intention is portrayed as a consumer's readiness to purchase a particular product, with pre-known information to reduce risk and increase customer purchase intention [22]. The reflection of the crave to purchase can be watched at the arrange of the client in sorting out among a few brand alternatives, after which he at last makes a buy that comes from numerous contemplations [23]. The arrange to purchase an item can be reflected as an exertion from a mental explanation that portrays buying intrigued [24]. A circumstance that reflects a person's purposeful to buy a item or benefit from a company or industry can happen since of a solid crave and drive that emerges from the intellect [25].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In figure 1 below, there is a research model and the relationship between variables based on library studies and previous research.

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

Figure 1, illustrates the study model and the study hypotheses were formulated :

- H1: Technology has a significant influence on smartphone purchase intention
- H2: Price has a significant influence on smartphone purchase intention
- H3: E-Wom has a significant influence on smartphone purchase intention
- H4: Technology has a significant influence on e-wom
- H5: Price has a significant influence on e-wom
- H6: The relationship between technology and smartphone purchase intention can be mediated by e-wom
- H7: The relationship between price and smartphone purchase intention can be mediated by e-wom

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

In this study, the authors used quantitative methods. The author sends an online questionnaire link via Whatsapp, Instagram, Facebook, Telegram, and LinkedIn. The authors utilized 311 substantial respondents for the analysis. In this research, the authors utilized the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with SmartPLS 3.0 to assess measurements and structural models.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data on respondents' characteristics were obtained from questionnaires that had been distributed to 311 respondents domiciled in Jabodetabek. The findings of this study are based on gender, namely that women are 59% and men are 41%, thus respondents between men and women are relatively balanced. Respondents were mostly between the ages of 26 and 41, with 59 percent of them being a percentage, which in this age range belonging to the millennial category. In the remaining income of respondents, most of them are around Rp. 1,200,000 – Rp. 6,000,000/month with a percentage of 50%. Furthermore, in Table 1 there are the results of data analysis that have been processed and the following analysis.

Variable	Items	Outer Loadings	CR	CA	AVE
TECHNOLOGY	TEC1	0.825	0.893	0.840	0.678
	TEC2	0.713			
	TEC3	0.811			
	TEC4	0.864			
PRICE	PRC2	0.941	0.907	0.842	0.768
	PRC3	0.937			
	PRC4	0.735			
E-WOM	EWM1	0.833	0.889	0.813	0.728
	EWM2	0.827			
	EWM3	0.898			
PURCHASE INTENTION	PI1	0.755	0.861	0.787	0.608
	PI2	0.744			
	PI3	0.835			
	PI4	0.780			

Table 1: Construct Reliability and Validity Results

The indicator has good validity and reliability if the outer loading value, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach Alpha value are greater than 0.70 [26]. In addition, it is also accompanied by an AVE value greater than 0.5. As shown in Table 1, all the outer loading, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach Alpha values of this study exceeded 0.7 and the AVE values exceeded 0.5. Based on these results, it can be said that all variables are valid and reliable.

In addition, in this study, there was an HTMT test, where this method was used to take advantage of the validity of discriminants. This is used for basic measurements using the multitrait-multimethod matrix method. The restraint of the HTMT value must be less than 0.9 to ensure the validity of the discriminant between two reflective constructions [27]. HTMT test results appeared a value of less than 0.90. The results below can be stated that all constructs have been valid in discriminant validity based on HTMT calculations.

	E-WOM	PRICE	PURCHASE INTENTION
E-WOM			
PRICE	0.413		
PURCHASE INTENTION	0.871	0.437	
TECHNOLOGY	0.138	0.089	0.350

Table 2: HTMT Results

Variable	R-Square	Q-Square
E-WOM	0.127	0.084
PURCHASE INTENTION	0.573	0.328

Table 3: Coefficient of determination (R2) & (Q2)

	E-WOM	PURCHASE INTENTION
E-WOM		0.874
PRICE	0.131	0.026

TECHNOLOGY	0.009	0.108
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Table 4: Effect Size (f2)

R-square is a measure of the proportion of variation in the value of an influenced variable that can be explained by the variable that affects it [26]. The R-square value for the purchase intent variable is 0.573 which means moderate. In addition to the Q-square value, the test shows that the purchase intent value is greater than zero indicating that the model already meets the relevant predictive value. While the smallest f-square value is indicated by the technology variable against e-wom and the strongest is indicated by the e-wom variable against purchase intent. Furthermore, there are the results of the hypothesis test of direct influence and indirect influence in table 5.

Research Hypothesis	T-Statistic	P-Value	Results
H 1 TECHNOLOGY → PURCHASE INTENTION	3.738	0.000	Significant
H 2 PRICE → PURCHASE INTENTION	2.457	0.014	Significant
H 3 E-WOM → PURCHASE INTENTION	13.303	0.000	Significant
H 4 TECHNOLOGY → E-WOM	1.349	0.178	Not significant
H 5 PRICE → E-WOM	5.608	0.000	Significant
H 6 TECHNOLOGY → E-WOM → PURCHASE INTENTION	1.344	0.179	Not significant
H 7 PRICE → E-WOM → PURCHASE INTENTION	5.043	0.000	Significant

Table 5: Results of Hypothesis Testing

Based on the results of hypothesis test one, there is a positive and significant influence of technology on purchase intentions. This can be interpreted to mean that the better the smartphone technology, the higher the intention to purchase smartphones by consumers. The latest technology, becomes the attraction of consumers when they make the decision to buy a smartphone [28].

In this case, it is the software that is the top priority of consumers in buying smartphones. In addition, ease of access and ease of use are also considerations for consumers in buying smartphones. This is in line with the research of which suggests that the ease of use and benefits of smartphones have a very significant role in shaping consumer intentions toward smartphone purchases [29].

In addition, that features also positively affect consumers' intention to buy smartphones. The design, model, operating system, camera, and other gadgets pull in the consideration of consumers when it comes to buying a smartphone [17]. There is a positive and significant influence of price on purchase intentions, so the second hypothesis is tested. This can be interpreted to mean that the more suitable the price of the smartphone with consumers, the higher the intention to purchase smartphones by consumers.

This research is in line with the results which states that customers are very delicate subjects because the work of consumers varies, so there are consumers who can only afford smartphones at a price that suits their abilities, and there are even consumers who cannot afford smartphones [17]. In this case, companies got to make favorable condition for consumers by offering products with a medium cost extend to consumers so that they can bear to pay for the smartphone they require themselves. In addition, with alluring costs, their deliberate in buying smartphones has expanded.

In addition, smartphone technology is developing rapidly, there are still many consumers who are not aware of these advances. There are only certain categories of consumers who are aware of this and want a smartphone that is high-tech. These consumers intend to buy expensive brands by considering various factors, one of which is price, when consumers intend to buy a smartphone, they assume that a high-priced smartphone is technically better than a smartphone at a lower price, so this is what increases the purchase intention of consumers in that particular class [28]. This is also stated by the results of research that price has a positive influence on smartphone purchase intentions in Jakarta [30].

There is a positive and significant influence of e-wom on purchase intentions, so the third hypothesis is tested. This can be interpreted to mean that the more positive the smartphone e-wom, the higher the intention to purchase smartphones by consumers. The results of this study are in line with the results of research which states that when consumers intend to buy, consumers will examine comments/reviews on websites, forums, blogs, to guarantee their purchase intentions are correct [17].

That consumers will be expected to purchase smartphones since of dependable online reviews through social media such as Youtube. In this case, online reviews can be utilized as a reference and guidance by consumers who will make smartphone purchases through reviews either through social media or on Youtube [31]. The online review is one of the important consideration factors for consumers who have the intention to buy a smartphone, so that the smartphone business can make event activities together reviewing and testimonializing smartphone products directly with celebrities, and reviews from YouTubers about gadgets in locations such as malls, modern stores and so on to increase purchase intention [32].

There is a positive and insignificant influence of technology on e-wom, so the fourth hypothesis is rejected. This can be interpreted to mean that smartphone technology,

is not enough to make consumers use e-wom as a reference in buying smartphones. Discrepancies can occur because consumers want to use technology that suits their wishes. Based on this, consumers no longer rely on information through e-wom, because the most important thing for consumers is to get an experience and experience directly from the smartphone technology they want [33]

There is a positive and significant effect on e-wom, so the fifth hypothesis is tested. This can be interpreted to mean that the more suitable the price of a smartphone, it makes consumers want to use e-wom as a reference in buying a smartphone. In the digital era, many consumers seek opinions from others online before buying a product. In this case, price awareness influences the search for opinions of potential consumers through e-wom [34].

Consumers want a price that matches the quality of the smartphone they will spend a certain amount. The price information that consumers get from online media has a more positive impact and this makes consumers more able to accept the perceived price of the product, regardless of whether the price is beyond consumer expectations or not [35]. In addition, there is conformity with research, which shows that payment instruments significantly affect e-wom, while online payment methods, it has a significant effect on e-wom [36].

Based on the results about the sixth hypothesis test, it can be concluded that e-wom does not play a full role in mediation between technology and purchase intention. This shows that reviews of technology on smartphones do not play a role in increasing the intention to buy smartphones. These discrepancies can occur because consumers want a variety of technologies which in this case can be in terms of hardware or software, which suits their wishes. This means that if consumers want to use technology that suits their wishes, then consumers no longer rely on information through e-wom, because the most important thing for consumers is to want to experience and experience directly from the technology they want. This is what makes e-wom no longer the mediator in increasing smartphone purchase intentions [33].

Based on the results of the seventh hypothesis test, it can be concluded that e-wom plays a partial role as a mediation between technology and purchase intent. This partial mediation applies because the direct path between the price variable and purchase intention has a significant influence, while the indirect path also has a significant influence. This shows that reviews about the price on smartphones are enough to have a role to increase the intention to buy a smartphone.

Nowadays, the internet is progressively utilized in sales, purchase, and payment transactions. To ensure the implementation of secure online transactions, it is important for customers to be able to select a reliable electronic payment method [37]. In addition, price awareness has an important role in influencing the search for opinions through e-wom. This will eventually lead to consumers' intention to buy products through social media [34].

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Samsung has several smartphone series that accommodate consumer needs, namely the Galaxy Series M and A are included in the low-end category, and the Galaxy Series S, Galaxy Series Z, and Galaxy Note are included in the high-end category. The price range offered also varies, ranging from one million to tens of millions of rupiah. Based on this price range, this study will also discuss two categories of smartphones, namely low-end and high-end.

A. Smartphone Low-end

For the low-end smartphone type, Samsung has a competitor, Xiaomi. This is because both are low-end smartphones that are widely recommended by websites and smartphone reviewers [8][9][10][13]. For ease in operating technology, learning the features in smartphones, and flexibility in using various features on smartphones, Samsung is equivalent to Xiaomi because it already has features and interface systems that make it easier for consumers to operate smartphones [38].

For hardware quality, such as battery life, storage memory, sound devices, and software, such as operating systems (android, iOS, etc.), Samsung is no better than Xiaomi [8][9][10][11][39][40][41]. This makes Samsung need to improve specifications for battery life, screen size, internal storage, RAM, and CPU speed. For prices that match consumer expectations, payment instruments, and payment methods, Samsung is already on par with Xiaomi [42][44]. On the refund guarantee for online payments, Samsung compares favorably with Xiaomi [43][45].

Furthermore, for the media used to disseminate information and reviewer credibility, Samsung is equivalent to Xiaomi in disseminating information related to their smartphones and has been reviewed by websites and gadget reviewers who have good credibility [38][46]. As for the content of reviews from gadget reviewers and other user comments, Samsung is no better compared to Xiaomi [8][9][10][13][41][47][48]. Based on reviews from smartphone websites and reviewers, Samsung needs to increase screen size, camera, and CPU speed, fast charging support, and enlarge internal storage. Based on user comments from online forums and e-commerce, Samsung needs to improve the design of the smartphone, internal memory, and screen size along with anti-scratch protectors and cameras.

B. Smartphone High-end

For the high-end smartphone type, Samsung has a competitor, namely Apple. This is because both are high-end smartphones that are widely recommended by websites and smartphone reviewers [8][9][10][13][14][15][16]. For ease in operating technology and learning the features in smartphones, Samsung already has features and interface systems that make it easier for consumers to operate smartphones [38][49].

For hardware quality, such as battery life, storage memory, sound devices, and software, such as operating systems (android, iOS, etc.), Samsung is better than Apple, but there are drawbacks in battery life, so Samsung needs to

increase battery life in order to support the performance of the smartphone [50][51][52][53]. As for the flexibility in using various features on smartphones, Samsung can be said to be better compared to Apple. For prices that match consumer expectations, Samsung is better than Apple. Furthermore, for payment instruments, payment methods and refund guarantees for online payments, Samsung and Apple are equivalent [54][55][56]

Furthermore, for the media used to disseminate information and reviewer credibility, Samsung is equivalent to Apple in disseminating information related to their smartphones and has been reviewed by websites and gadget reviewers who have good credibility [38][46].

As for the content of reviews from gadget reviewers, Samsung is better than Apple and for other users' comments, Samsung is on par with Apple [50][51][52][53][57].

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

The results appeared that technology, price, and e-wom have a significant positive relationship with smartphone purchase intentions. In addition, the price has a significant effect on e-wom, but not for technology. The e-wom variable can mediate between price and purchase intention, but e-wom cannot mediate technology and purchase intention.

Based on the comparison of technology with its competitors, for the low-end smartphone category, Samsung needs to improve specifications for battery life, screen size, internal storage, RAM, and CPU speed. In addition, based on reviews from websites and smartphone reviewers, Samsung needs to increase the screen size, camera, CPU speed, fast charging support, and enlarge the internal storage. Meanwhile, from the comments of users of online forums and e-commerce, Samsung needs to improve the smartphone design, internal memory, screen size along with anti-scratch protectors and cameras. Based on the comparison of technology with its competitors, for the high-end smartphone category, Samsung needs to improve battery life, in order to support the performance of the smartphone.

Further research can add other variables such as brand image, social influence, lifestyle, and others that can cause consumers' intention to buy smartphones. In addition, it can also develop research models by developing populations and samples that are more varied and not limited to Jabodetabek only. In addition, for further research, it is necessary to re-examine the relationship of technology, price, and e-wom variables to purchase intentions with different products.

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